

organic C, 1.90% active Fe, 13 ppm Bray's P₁ P, 136 ppm exchangeable K, 0.66 ppm DTPA-Zn, 0.70 ppm DTPA-Cu, and water table <25 cm) to study the response of rice cultivar PP₂-34-155-7 to Zn and Cu. The greatest yield response,

1.2 t/ha, was recorded with 4 kg Cu/ha; it almost equaled the 1.1 t/ha from 12 kg Zn/ha (Table 2). The significant increase in grain uptake of Zn, Cu, Mn, P, and K over the control and the simultaneous reduction in Fe might have

led to proper nutrient balance and efficient use.

Proper use of P, K, Zn, and Cu fertilizer after soil and plant tissue tests can successfully mitigate Fe toxicity at these sites. □

Effects of P on growth and uptake of Cu and Fe in rice grown in excess Cu

S. Greipsson, School of Biological Sciences, University of East Anglia, Norwich, NR4 7TJ, UK

We examined the effect of increased P concentration on rice cultivar M-201 84 Biggs grown with and without excess Cu. Plants grew in a 1/4-strength Hoagland's solution with different combinations of Cu, P, and MES (2[N-Morpholine] ethanesulfonic acid). Excess Cu concentration was 0.5 mg/liter and increased P concentration was equal to full-strength Hoagland's solution. MES buffer was pH 6.0.

We grew seedlings hydroponically for 40 d: first for 15 d in a 1/2-strength Hoagland's solution and then for 25 d with five plants in each of six treatments (Table 1).

Same-sized plants were grown in 5-liter black buckets in a growth chamber

(Conviron CMP 2023) in a 16/8 h light/dark regime; temperature was 27 °C in light and 22 °C in darkness. Solutions were changed every other day; pH 6 and 70% humidity were maintained.

Plant samples were digested for 12 h at 120 °C with 2 ml HNO₃ and 1 ml H₂O₂ in a Teflon pressure chamber. Cu, Fe, and P concentrations were measured by flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (Perkin Elmer 2830).

Plants in the excess Cu solutions grew poorly (Table 1). Plants in Cu + P and Cu + MES + P solutions showed toxicity symptoms (yellow leaves, necrosis of leaf tips, stunted growth); plants in Cu + MES solution had less extensive symptoms. P appeared to increase the toxicity of excess Cu.

Leaf tips had higher Cu concentrations in the excess Cu solutions, but Cu exposure lowered Fe concentrations in leaf tips. Plants in the solutions containing Cu had higher Fe and Cu concentrations in the roots than plants not receiving Cu, suggesting synergistic uptake (Table 2).

The high Fe accumulation in roots, but low Fe concentration in leaf tips in Cu + P solution, may have resulted from coprecipitation of Fe in the cortical root layer and inhibited growth in leaf tips. MES buffer did not affect Fe, Cu, or P concentrations in leaf tips or roots. Plants grown in excess Cu solution without added P have greater biomass because of high internal P concentrations.

P concentration in leaf tips in the Cu + P and Cu + MES + P solutions were much higher than that of plants in the Cu + MES solution. High P concentration in leaf tips lowered the amount of metabolically active Fe²⁺ that could compete with heavy metals (such as Cu) for metabolically sensitive sites inside leaves. □

Fertilizer management

Integrated nitrogen management for irrigated lowland rice

A. R. M. Haroon, R. Krishnasamy, V. Velu, D. Jawahar, and P. P. Ramazaswami, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Killikulam, Vallanad 627252, Tamil Nadu, India

We conducted three experiments that combined organic and inorganic sources to supply the N required by lowland transplanted rice on a Typic Ustropept.

Soil had pH 8.1, soluble salt concentration 0.4 dS/m, 160 ppm alkaline KMnO₄-extractable N, 8.6 ppm 0.5 M NaHCO₃-extractable P, 135 ppm NH₄OAc-extractable K, and 0.32% organic C.

Test crops were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications: IR20 during 1988 pishanam (Oct-Feb), ADT36 during 1989 kar (Jun-

Table 1. Effect of P on size of plants in solutions containing excess Cu.^a

Treatment	Biomass (g)	Leaf length (cm)	Root dry weight (g)	Leaf dry weight (g)
Cu+MES	2.3 ± 0.1 c	53.4 ± 1.9 a	0.09 ± 0.01 b	0.29 ± 0.01 b
Cu+P	1.3 ± 0.2 e	43.9 ± 0.8 b	0.06 ± 0.005 c	0.12 ± 0.02 c
Cu+MES+P	1.7 ± 0.1 d	43.2 ± 0.6 b	0.08 ± 0.002 b	0.22 ± 0.009 bc
P+MES	2.4 ± 0.1 bc	59.4 ± 1.3 a	0.1 ± 0.006 ab	0.42 ± 0.03 a
P	2.9 ± 0.2 a	58.1 ± 3.9 a	0.1 ± 0.01 a	0.46 ± 0.04 a
MES	2.8 ± 0.1 ab	58.3 ± 3.4 a	0.1 ± 0.004 a	0.41 ± 0.02 a

^aWithin columns, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level

Table 2. Chemical analysis of plants grown in a 1/4 strength Hoagland's solution with or without added P, Cu, or buffer (MES).

Treatment	Leaves				Roots		
	Fe (µg/g)	Cu (µg/g)	P (mg/g)	Fe/P	Fe (µg/g)	Cu (µg/g)	Fe/Cu
Cu+MES	91 ^a	44	2.0	455	4200	1630	3
Cu+P	87	49	11.5	76	7120	1370	5
Cu+MES+P	97	50	11.9	82	6250	1010	6
P+MES	107	26	7.4	145	1130	91	12
P	108	22	7.3	147	1330	97	14
MES	111	31	2.0	555	1150	124	9

^aValues are means from 5 plants in each treatment.

Apparent N recovery, N uptake, and yield of rice under integrated N management. Killikulam, India, 1988–89.

Treatment ^a	1988 pishanam			1989 kar			1989 pishanam		
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)
T1 - control	1.4	33		4.0	96		3.0	76	—
100 kg N/ha as									
T2 - urea	3.1	87	54	5.3	148	52	5.5	137	61
T3 - FYM	1.9	49	16	4.7	141	45	5.3	140	64
T4 - <i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	3.3	81	48	4.8	132	36	5.7	156	80
T5 - azolla	2.1	58	25	5.1	124	28	5.7	143	67
T6 - <i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	^b	^b	^b	4.5	120	24	5.3	146	70
50 kg N/ha as urea + 50 kg N/ha as									
T7 - FYM	2.7	76	43	4.8	124	28	5.7	143	67
T8 - <i>S. aculeata</i>	3.1	82	49	4.7	148	52	4.8	141	65
T9 - azolla	3.1	83	50	4.6	112	16	5.9	154	78
T10 - <i>C. juncea</i>	^b	^b	^b	7.3	142	46	5.3	145	69
1/3 N/ha each as									
T11 - <i>S. aculeata</i> + azolla + urea	3.3	94	61	4.4	108	12	5.5	128	52
T12 - <i>C. juncea</i> + azolla + urea	^b	^b	^b	4.8	108	12	6.3	151	75
T13 - <i>C. juncea</i> + urea + <i>Azospirillum</i>	^b	^b	^b	5.1	128	32	5.3	149	73
LSD (0.05)	0.2	20	22	0.55	22	21	0.4	11	11

^aTo supply 100 kg N/ha, 25 t *S. aculeata* or *C. juncea* was applied 15 d before transplanting (DBT), 20 t FYM and 25 t azolla were applied 1 DBT. Urea was applied in 3 splits: 50% basal + 25% each at tillering (30 d after transplanting [DT] and panicle initiation stage [60 DTI]). *Azospirillum* was applied as seedling dip and main field soil application. ^bTreatments not tried during 1988 pishanam.

Sep) and 1989 pishanam. Treatments were a complete N dose (100 kg N/ha) either in full or in combination with organic sources and fertilizer N (see table).

The N content of the organic sources used on a dry weight basis were 0.5% for farmyard manure (FYM), 3.2% for *Sesbania aculeata*, and 4.0% for azolla during 1988 pishanam and 0.5% for FYM, 3.3% for *S. aculeata*, 3.4% for *Crotalaria juncea*, and 4.0% for azolla during 1989 kar. Organic N sources were not applied during 1989 pishanam, but the full N dose was applied as prilled urea in three splits.

S. aculeata applied alone or in combination with azolla and urea gave yields similar to those from a full dose of urea N in 1988 pishanam. N applied 50% through *C. juncea* and 50% through urea produced 37% higher yields than a full dose applied as urea during 1989 kar. Applying a full N dose as *C. juncea* + azolla + urea during 1989 pishanam recorded 15% higher yield than a full dose of urea N.

In 1989 pishanam and kar, substituting *S. aculeata* for the N requirement, either fully or at half level, recorded a N recovery equal to application of a full dose of N as urea. □

Grain yields of rainfed rice - lentil as affected by N fertilizer and biofertilizer

N. R. Das and B. Datta, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, West Bengal (WB), India

We evaluated the relative efficiency of biofertilizers *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Corchorus olitorius* L. and N levels (0, 50, and 100 kg/ha) from urea on grain yield of transplanted rainfed rice during the 1990 summer and wet seasons and of residual lentil during 1990–91 winter in WB.

Soil was clayey loam with 0.61% organic C, 0.062% total N, 15 kg available P, 160 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8.

Seeds of green manure crops *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata* were broadcast on 7 May 1990 at 30 kg seed/ha and of leaf manure crop *C. olitorius* (cultivar Basudev) at 7 kg seed/ha in a split-plot design with four

replications. The control was left fallow. Green and leaf manures were incorporated in a 7- × 5-m plot on 17 Jul.

On 8 Aug, 30-d-old IR36 rice seedlings were transplanted in subplots with 4 seedlings/hill at 25- × 10-cm spacing. We applied 20 kg/ha each of P and K and half of each N treatment. The other half was applied 30 d after transplanting. Rice was harvested 4 Nov.

Lentil (*Lens culinaris* L. cultivar B77) seeds at 15 kg/ha were broadcast over the standing rice one day before it was

harvested. Lentil was harvested 10 Feb.

Rice grain yields with green manure from *S. rostrata* or *S. aculeata* were significantly higher than those with either leaf manure from *C. olitorius* or the control.

Rice yields increased significantly as N levels increased. Rice yields with *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata* increased equally with both 50 and 100 kg N/ha. Neither biofertilizer nor N level significantly affected lentil grain yield (see table). □

Effect of N fertilizer and biofertilizer on grain yield of transplanted rainfed rice and the aftereffects on lentil. West Bengal, India, 1990–91.

Treatment	Rice and lentil grain yields (t/ha)					
	No N		50 kg N/ha		100 kg N/ha	
	Rice	Lentil	Rice	Lentil	Rice	Lentil
Fallow (control)	2.1	1.1	3.2	1.0	3.5	0.7
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	3.2	1.2	3.1	0.6	4.9	0.4
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	3.2	0.6	4.0	0.8	4.4	1.0
<i>Corchorus olitorius</i>	2.5	1.1	2.7	0.7	3.4	0.9
LSD (0.05)	0.7	ns	0.4	ns	0.8	ns